

One for all or the more the better? A survey of ready-to-use AI tools for literature review

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Abstract

Driven by the recent progress in artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, a remarkable number of specialized software tools for automating academic literature reviews with the help of AI have emerged. The functional characteristics of these tools differ widely, ranging from rather simple search tools to interactive literature maps to complex solutions for whole systematic literature reviews. This paper presents a systematic overview of the current landscape of ready-to-use AI-based tools for literature review based on functional characteristics and implemented AI methods. Based on 56 tools collected through a multivocal review complemented by a web search, we developed a conceptual framework and a functional classification with six categories. Our results reveal both competing and complementary tools along the review process and show the potential usefulness of a structured tool selection approach.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, systematic literature review, automation, research tools.

Introduction

Literature reviews are an indispensable and well-established methodological step at the beginning of every research process (Levy & J. Ellis, 2006; Sauer & Seuring, 2023; vom Brocke et al., 2015). Even before the launch of ChatGPT in 2022, numerous specialized software tools for scientific literature reviews have appeared claiming to fasten and ease the review process with the help of artificial intelligence (AI) (de la Torre-López et al., 2023). Along with the dynamic evolution of AI, the number of these AI-based literature tools is growing rapidly (Tingelhoff et al., 2024). Among these tools are specialized systems for certain steps in the review process like literature search or data analysis as well as integrated solutions claiming to support systematic literature reviews (SLR) from start to end. Against this background, it becomes more and more difficult and time consuming for researchers to find the right tool or tool combination for their individual

literature review. To address this problem, we conducted an exploratory study of the current landscape of ready-to-use AI-based literature review tools guided by two research questions:

RQ1. How can AI-based software tools support a researcher or research group in preparing a literature review?

RQ2. What do AI-assisted literature tools have in common and where do they differ?

Ready to use software products (RUSP) are “available to any user, at cost or not, to use without the need to conduct development activities” (ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765:2017, p. 365), for instance, compiling source code. Because most of the tools collected for this survey do not provide detailed information on their technical implementation, we analyzed them as black boxes. The study aims to provide an overview of what AI-based literature tools are in the field and what they can be used for. Thereby we contribute to a broader understanding of AI integration in literature reviews and offer practical advice for researchers to select and combine the right tools with limited knowledge of their technical implementation.

Theoretical Background and Related Work

From the IS perspective, an AI tool is a system in which a human uses AI-based information technology to perform a (semi-)automated task. In line with Levy and Ellis (Levy & J. Ellis, 2006), we interpret the task of literature review as an input-processing-output model with information both as in- and output. A well-established research framework for assessing the individual performance of IS-technology is the theory of task-technology fit (TTF) (Goodhue & Thompson, 1995) that described performance as a factor depending on the match between task and technology characteristics (Cane & McCarthy, 2009). We draw on the TTF theory for this study since it has demonstrated to be useful and valid for AI-based systems (Gupta et al., 2024).

The question of how AI can support the preparation of literature reviews has received increasing attention from scientists across many disciplines recently. From screening the available literature on using AI for literature reviews it becomes clear that the existing studies can be divided into three research streams related to ChatGPT: 1) studies published before the breakthrough of Large Language Models (LLM) marked by ChatGPT, 2) studies on the use of ChatGPT and other general-purpose GPTs, and 3) studies on a new wave of generative AI (GenAI) tools specializing on literature reviews. The AI methods used by today’s RUSP for literature review have been developed by researchers before. The survey by de la Torre-López et al. (2023) explored the AI methods proposed between 2006 and 2021 to automate systematic analyses of scientific literature. The paper describes algorithm types and available tools, where most of the latter are research prototypes. Previous studies on AI methods for automating literature reviews include, for example, Jonnalagadda et al. (2015) and Dann et al. (2017)

Triggered by the immense interest in ChatGPT, several studies have analyzed its potential use for automating literature reviews (e.g., Alshami et al., 2023; Haman & Školník, 2024; Mostafapour et al., 2024; Qureshi et al., 2023; Syriani et al., 2024). But since ChatGPT and the underlying LLM

are designed for general-purpose use, research on and development of specialized AI-based tools (some applying GPT/LLM) has continued in parallel.

Pinzolit (2023) gave a brief overview of selected AI-based tools for academic use divided into the three application fields 1) literature search (9 tools), 2) analyzing research articles (7), and 3) academic writing and editing (6). He concludes that AI tools have the potential to transform academic research and education but also pose challenges for assessing the authenticity and quality of academic work, and that academics must stay updated and critically evaluate these tools. Bolaños et al. (2024) conducted a survey of 21 AI-based literature tools aiming at their use for semi-automation in the screening and extraction phases of systematic literature reviews. Of the 21 tools investigated, 12 specialize in evidence-based medicine, pharmacy, and related disciplines by using data from sources like PubMed or implementing special functions related to clinical trials (e.g., LitSuggest, RobotReviewer). In their explorative scoping review study, Mozelius and Humble (2024) concentrated on generative AI tools. They analyzed 11 studies from 2019 to 2023 to find out which and how GenAI tools can be of use in literature reviews. Although they discovered a “wide variety of tools”, the authors still recommended using them solely as supportive aids, ensuring that the human-in-the-loop remains in control. In addition, the ethical aspects of using GenAI in literature reviews need further research. Schryen et al. (2025) examined the role of GenAI in literature reviews with a special focus on knowledge development. Using an epistemological approach, they explored how GenAI can assist alongside six key knowledge development activities. As a result, the authors describe the capabilities as well as limitations of GenAI and offer recommendations in support of knowledge development. In line with Mozelius and Humble (2024), GenAI is not estimated as a replacement for the human researcher but as a complementary tool. From the available literature, we found no research providing a comprehensive and structured overview of the evolving AI-based tool landscape in view of practical use for literature reviews using an empirical approach.

Research Methodology

In pursuit of our research goal to provide an overview of existing AI-based RUSP for literature review, we designed a structured review process that combines an empirical approach with a multivocal literature review for data collection. As our review topic, we defined specialized AI-based software tools with specific support for tasks that are required or useful for conducting scientific literature reviews. These tools must be available as a ready-to-use package or service, excluding experimental prototypes without institutional support and tools that require manual installation or are only available as source code. We also excluded literature and citation databases, even when they offer integrated AI enhancements for literature search (e.g., Semantic Scholar, the Open Research Knowledge Graph ORKG, or ResearchGate’s recommendation algorithm). Furthermore, out of scope are vanilla AI chatbots based on general-purpose GPTs (e.g., ChatGPT, Google Gemini or Microsoft Copilot) as well as GPTs optimized for research in general (e.g., ChatGPT Deep Research, Scholar GPT, or Gemini AI co-scientist).

For collecting relevant tools, we conducted a multivocal literature review and a complementary web search between December 2024 and March 2025. A multivocal review (Garousi et al., 2019) extends the scope of peer-reviewed publications with grey literature and online content from the Internet (e.g., blog posts and white papers). We decided on this type of review due to the rapid development and diffusion of AI technology, which outpaces scientific publication cycles (Tingelhoff et al., 2024). As a starting point, we screened the state-of-the-art literature presented in the previous section. For both the multivocal review and the web search, we used the search string “(artificial intelligence OR AI OR automated) AND (literature review OR literature search OR literature screening OR literature analysis)” and applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria listed in Table 1. From the initial search, we collected a data set with 74 tools, from which we excluded 18 tools by applying our criteria. A full list of the remaining 56 tools we investigated in this survey can be found in Table A.1 of the appendix. Of the 18 excluded tools, we found 14 tools with an explicit focus on health research/evidence-based medicine/clinical trials, often using PubMed as a data source exclusively. While we excluded these tools due to our IS perspective, they might nevertheless be considered interesting because of their technological approach and potentially useful for other disciplines. Therefore, they are also listed in Table A.2.

Table 1. Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion	Exclusion
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific support of literature review tasks for research • AI-based • Interdisciplinary, not specialized • Ready-to-use • Official website available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other research use cases • Not AI-based • Specialized in health research/ evidence-based medicine • Not ready-to-use • No website available

As a foundation for investigating and classifying the collected tools, we defined a conceptual framework based on the TTF theory, established guidelines for literature reviews, and findings from the state-of-the-art of automating literature reviews. This framework is illustrated in Figure 1 and described in the following section.

Because of our practical user-oriented focus on the one hand and a lack of detailed information on the technical AI implementation of many tools on the other hand, we defined six tool categories based on their main functional characteristics related to literature review tasks. The functional characteristics that constitute a category were generalized by examining the functional profile of the collected tools based on information from the vendor’s website and referenced information (e.g., YouTube videos). Some of the tools have been developed as part of or based on published research (e.g., Ammirato et al., 2023), while other tools were covered in review articles (e.g., Behera et al., 2023). To test the proposed functional characteristics, we selected for each category the three tools for which our search produced the most detailed information. For these selected tools, we asked the vendors for further information with a brief semi-structured questionnaire via e-mail. Finally, we reviewed the tools listed in Table 2 again to feature the characteristics of the respective category based on the collected information.

Conceptual framework

For conceptualizing AI-assisted literature reviews, we draw on the TTF theory to frame the central tasks of the literature review process, the researcher conducting it, and the AI-based tool within three layers: 1) human/user, 2) task, and 3) technology layer as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework for AI-Assisted Literature Reviews

With respect to our focus on RUSP, the researcher's perspective on AI-based review tools is described by AI competencies according to Almatrafi et al. (2024). The competencies point to first directions for what to consider in search of the best fit between the task 'literature review' and the technology 'AI tool'. While functional characteristics can be derived from the task layer, the competences indicate quality characteristics like, for instance, understanding the applied AI methods and what data is used to facilitate evaluating the output information quality. Also, ethical aspects are to be considered, according to the 'handle responsibly' competency. The task is described by steps according to the integrated SLR process proposed by Tingelhoff et al. (2024), which was synthesized from a recent state-of-the-art review. The AI-based system is structured as an input-processing-output, on which only limited information is available, and the core AI component is considered from an outside view as a black box.

Results

AI Methods Applied by Literature Review Tools

Although claiming the use of AI methods, most of the identified literature review tools do not provide detailed information on their technical implementation and need to be considered as a black box, consequently. With respect to available information, we generalized the heterogeneous and unprecise AI specification to distinguish five non-disjunct categories: 1) Machine Learning (ML), 2) Natural Language Processing (NLP), 3) Large Language Model (LLM), 4) Vector Search/Database (VDB) and 5) Knowledge Graph (KG)/Citation Graph (CG), cf. Tables A.1 and A.2.

ML as a subfield of AI comprises many approaches and methods to give a software system “the ability to improve performance based on experience” (Russell & Norvig, 2022, p. 1). NLP enables machines to understand, interpret, and generate human language (e.g., by linguistic rules or ML) to process text and speech. NLP as technology evolved from rule-based (conventional software) systems in the 1950s (first simple chatbot) to statistical methods in the 1990s and deep-learning models like transformers in the 2010s. ML and NLP provide a variety of methods, their combinations and the concrete models to enable ‘AI-based’ applications (e.g., in human-like text generation, translation or even in literature review), as discussed in this paper. For tools with method entry “ML” in Tables A.1 and A.2, more specific information was not available.

An LLM – state-of-the-art in NLP and generative AI – is trained on huge text datasets to generate human-like responses and to facilitate text generation, summarization, or reasoning. The ‘deep’ architecture of an underlying transformer/NN model (Vaswani et al., 2017) requires elaborate pre-training by the model provider and constitutes a model class, Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT). A general-purpose LLM/GPT can be fine-tuned with domain-specific knowledge from the user context. The alternative training of a Small Language Model (SLM) or a classic statistical LM allows for more specific use cases and saves resources.

VDB provides a quick retrieval of similar data points in high-dimensional spaces (text, image, audio) by nearest-neighbor search for recommendation systems or search engines (cf. Malkov & Yashunin, 2020). Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) to improve the domain-specific responses of LLMs is often VDB-based. A KG is a structured database for entities and their relationships (cf. Paulheim, 2017). Linked data points can enable more context-aware answers or enhance the search relevance. A KG can also represent a network of scientific publications (CG). State-of-the-art Semantic Analysis (SA) and Similarity Calculation are NLP steps and thus listed among AI methods, too.

Categories by Functional Characteristics

The six functional categories described in this section are non-disjunctive and partially building on each other. The basic characteristics of category 1) search & discover apply also to most tools in the other categories, except category 4) analyze data where tools typically start with existing

paper/data collections. Tools of category 6) full SLR support always include characteristics for search & discover (category 1) as well as data analysis (category 4), but not necessarily from the other categories. Categories 2) to 5) may also overlap in the sense that tools from one category have individual characteristics from other categories. The assignment of a tool to its category is always based on its main functionality according to the available information.

1) Search & discover

Tools of this category help researchers to find relevant papers or data according to a user-defined search term/query string by utilizing identifiers (e.g., DOI), metadata (e.g., keywords), and semantic/vector search methods based on similarity and context. A tool may also use one or more uploaded/imported seed paper(s) to find and recommend related work, offer filters for search results (e.g., year published, citation count), and screen for topics. GenAI (GPT/LLM) may be used for answering questions (Q/A) and even generating search queries, bullet lists, or text outlines. The main functional characteristics of this category are listed in Table 2 and exemplified with three selected tools representative of this category.

2) Visualize & explore

Tools for creating graphical representations of related papers (called a literature map or graph), citations, or topics based on network or tree structures. Usually offering interactive functionality to explore the graph for accessing information on nodes (e.g., retrieve full text), backward and forward search along citations, and to manipulate the graph by adding or removing nodes. Exploring may also include getting recommendations for similar work or suggested authors. Require one or more seed papers as a starting point, and therefore includes features from category ‘search & discover’.

3) Assist reading

Tools that help researchers to quickly understand paper content by extracting and summarizing user-defined aspects, for instance, definitions, arguments, methods, findings, and keyword extractions. Utilize NLP, GPT, and LLM technology stacks to support natural language conversations (chat) or interactive prompting (K & Mathew, 2020). May also include search & discover features. The determining characteristics are stated in Table 2.

4) Analyze data

This category comprises specialized tools with advanced support of automated data analysis compared to the simpler screening features of most tools in category 1. Basically, data analysis comprises features to structure, extract, assess (e.g., risk of bias), and synthesize data from PDF files or other sources (Jonnalagadda et al., 2015). Since the focus is not on search and discovery, the data to be analyzed typically must be imported at the beginning (e.g., references, full text as PDF). In this category, we could find only a few tools, most of them with a focus on evidence-based medicine/health research (Schmidt et al., 2024). Nevertheless, depending on the SLR design, the tools in Table 2 might be useful.

Closely related are specialized tools for qualitative data analysis (QDA) like ATLAS.ti or MAXQDA, which also utilize AI. Because of our focus on literature reviews, we considered QDA tools out of scope.

5) Cite & write

Extends the prior categories with functional characteristics of an intelligent writing assistant integrated into a proprietary text editor component. These tools semi-automate writing by utilizing GenAI technologies in support of drafting an outline and text, brainstorming, summarization, etc. An additional functional focus lies also on inserting citations and respective bibliography into the written text in combination with literature review characteristics from categories 1-3. Some tools even include reference manager modules intending to replace stand-alone solutions like Zotero or Mendeley. Some of these tools may also qualify as academic writing assistants, but for this survey, they were selected because of their literature-related capabilities.

6) Full SLR support

Includes most or all characteristics of the categories 1-5 and adds features to integrate them into a workflow along the process of planning and conducting an SLR from an end-to-end user perspective. In Life Sciences, the so-called Cochrane Review is a popular SLR reference process (Higgins et al., 2019), supported by several full SLR tools listed in Tables A.1 and A.2 of the appendix (e.g., MySLR or Covidence). Data analysis features of full SLR tools might overlap with category 4, but also offer more SLR-specific features like risk of bias assessment. Organization and management of SLRs are supported on project, team, and institutional level, usually depending on the subscription plan. The full SLR support is completed with features for reporting and presenting the review results (e.g., PRISMA diagram, Page et al., 2021).

Table 2: Categorization of AI Tools for Literature Review

Category	Functional characteristics	Representative tools
1) Search & discover	a) term search, b) seed paper, c) filter, d) screen, e) paper dialog (Q/A), f) generate	Consensus, Keenious, ORKG Ask
2) Visualize & explore	a) literature map, b) citation graph, c) topic map, d) filter, e) explore	Connected Papers, Research Rabbit, Litmaps
3) Assist reading	a) summarize, b) compare, c) chat, d) mark/annotate, e) translate	Explainpaper, SciSpace, SciSummary
4) Analyze data	a) extract, b) assess, c) synthesize	Colandr, Dextr (beta), Dimensions
5) Cite & write	a) draft & edit text, b) paraphrase, c) insert citations, d) bibliography, e) manage references	AnswerThis, scite, WriteWise
6) Full SLR support	a) workflow support, b) analyze data, c) project level support, d) team level support, e) institutional level support, f) reporting	Elicit, MySLR, Rayyan

Discussion and Conclusion

From our six categories it becomes visible that the available ready-to-use AI-based tools for literature reviews basically offer the functional characteristics to semi-automate the review process from end to end. Full automation without the human in the loop is currently not feasible with the tools collected for this study. There are still many decision points in the process that require the researcher's human intervention. One of the first decisions to make is the selection of the right tool according to the researcher's individual requirements. While full SLR solutions have the benefits of integrated data, process and functionality, specialized tools might deliver better results for certain steps of the review process. Although we did not test and compare the performance of the tools in this study, we found that many of the existing full SLR solutions are designed to support highly standardized SLR protocols (e.g., the Cochrane review) and might not fit equally well with more individual reviews. In this case, a best-of-breed strategy might deliver the best results but brings up again the problem of the optimal tool selection.

The functional characteristics that make up the proposed categories can be used to position different tools against each other and gain a structured overview of the tool market. This might also serve as the entrance and foundation for a criteria-based tool selection process. The functional characteristics represent a starting point for developing more detailed operational selection criteria and measures. Nevertheless, a comprehensive selection process must also consider quality characteristics, as indicated by our conceptual framework. Especially quality and ethical concerns need to be addressed (Ngwenyama & Rowe, 2024; Qureshi et al., 2023). As a prerequisite for a sound quality and ethical evaluation of a tool transparency on its technical implementation is required, ideally by publishing the source code. Furthermore, suitable criteria and measures are required. The Open Science paradigm offers suitable standards and principles, like the FAIR principles for data management (Wilkinson et al., 2016). In the case of quality, the ISO standard 25010 Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuARE) describes established general models for both product quality and quality in use. These could be combined and complemented with scientific requirements on literature reviews (e.g., Cram, 2019).

Given the potential of AI to increase the speed and quantity of published research even further, the concept of a living systematic review (Elliott et al., 2014), a system capable of adding and screening literature automatically, also gains more relevance. Some of the existing full SLR solutions have already started to implement this vision (e.g., Pitts.ai, Laser AI, System Pro). On the way to establish this as a standard review model, further research and development is still required. Meanwhile the number of AI-based tools for literature reviews will certainly continue to grow and develop further regarding their functional characteristics. Further research toward a method for systematic evaluation and selection of AI literature tools therefore seems to be appropriate. Constructing such a method requires further criteria and procedures for tool performance comparison in terms of output quality as well as ethical considerations of using AI for research.

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Authors Biographies

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Oliver Jokisch, Dr.-Ing. is a professor of cybersecurity at the Meissen University of Applied Sciences (HSF) in Germany and the director of the Saxon Institute for Governance Innovation (SIVIM). Oliver has studied information technology at the TU Dresden and the Loughborough University (UK), graduating as a diploma engineer. He holds a Ph.D. degree from TUD and previously had a chair of system theory at the private university of Deutsche Telekom in Leipzig. His current research focuses on cybersecurity and AI application in audio, speech, and video communication.

Robin Vogel is a lecturer for management in public sector at the Meissen University of Applied Science (HSF) in Germany. After completing his Bachelor of Laws degree at Meissen University of Applied Sciences, he completed a master degree in human resources development at the RPTU University Kaiserslautern-Landau. His teaching and research areas are knowledge management, change management, process optimization and project management. He worked in various functions in human resources management in the city administration of Dresden.

Rico Blei is a research associate in the 4transfer joint project at Meissen University of Applied Science (HSF). Rico studied mechanical engineering (with a focus on lightweight construction) at the TU Dresden and graduated with a degree in engineering from the University of Wisconsin-Madison (USA). After working as a scientist in interdisciplinary projects in fields including bionics and medical technology, he currently focuses on knowledge and technology transfer in public administration.

Appendix

Table A.1. AI-Based Literature Review Tools (Interdisciplinary, not Specialized)¹

Name	Category	Launch year	App type ²	AI method(s)	Data source(s)	Cost	URL
ASReview LAB	Search & discover	2019	d	ML	Import	Free	https://asreview.nl/
Bohrium	Search & discover	n/a ³	w, m, d	LLM	n/a	Paid subs. ⁴	https://www.dp.tech/en/product/bohrium
Consensus	Search & discover	2022	w	LLM, Vector search	Semantic Scholar	Freemium	https://consensus.app/
Keenious	Search & discover	2022	w, d	Language model	OpenAlex	Freemium	https://keenious.com/
OiPub	Search & discover	2024	w	NLP	CrossRef, OpenAire	Free	https://oipub.com/
ORKG Ask	Search & discover	2019	w	Vector Search, LLM, KG	ORKG	Free	https://ask.orkg.org/
R Discovery	Search & discover	2018	w, m	n/a	n/a	Paid subs.	https://discovery.researcher.life/
Scinapse	Search & discover	2017	w	ML	n/a	Freemium	https://www.scinapse.io/
Sourcely	Search & discover	2023	w	LLM	n/a	Paid subs.	https://www.sourcely.net/
SWIFT Review	Search & discover	2015	d	ML	n/a	Free	https://www.sciome.com/swift-review/
Citation Gecko	Visualize & explore	2017	w	KG	n/a	Freemium	https://citationgecko.azurewebsites.net/
Citrus search	Visualize & explore	2024	w	KG	Semantic Scholar	Free	https://citrus-search.com/
Connected Papers	Visualize & explore	2020	w	KG	Semantic Scholar	Freemium	https://www.connectedpapers.com/
Inciteful	Visualize & explore	2021	w	KG	OpenAlex, Semantic Scholar, Crossref, OpenCitations	Free	https://inciteful.xyz/
Litmaps	Visualize & explore	2016	w	KG, SA	OpenAlex, Semantic	Freemium	https://www.litmaps.com/

¹ Sorted by 1) category and 2) name.

² w = web, m = mobile, d = desktop.

³ Not available.

⁴ Subscription.

Name	Category	Launch year	App type ²	AI method(s)	Data source(s)	Cost	URL
					Scholar and Crossref		
Open Knowledge Maps	Visualize & explore	2016	w	n/a	n/a	Free	https://openknowledgemaps.org/
Research Rabbit	Visualize & explore	2021	w	LLM, CG, SA	n/a	Freemium	https://www.researchrabbit.ai/
scienceOS	Visualize & explore	2023	w	NLP, ML, LLM	Semantic Scholar	Freemium	https://www.scienceos.ai/
Scopus AI	Visualize & explore	2024	w, m	LLM, Vector search, citation graph	Scopus	Paid subs.	https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/scopus-ai
ChatDOC	Assist reading	2023	w, m	n/a	n/a	Freemium	https://chatdoc.com/
ChatPDF	Assist reading	2023	w	NLP	n/a	Free	https://www.chatpdf.com/
enago Read	Assist reading	2021	w	NLP	n/a	Freemium	https://www.read.enago.com/
Explainpaper	Assist reading	2022	w	GPT	Import	Freemium	https://www.explainpaper.com/
Humata	Assist reading	2023	w	n/a	n/a	Freemium	https://www.humata.ai/
OpenRead	Assist reading	2023	w, m	LLM	n/a	Freemium	https://www.openread.academy/
Outread	Assist reading	2022	w, m	NLP	n/a	Free trial, paid subs.	https://outread.ai/
Paperguide	Assist reading	2023	w	NLP	n/a	Freemium	https://paperguide.ai/
Paperpal	Assist reading	2018	w, d	NLP, ML	n/a	Freemium	https://paperpal.com/
Petal	Assist reading	2018	w	LLM	Import	Freemium	https://www.petal.org/
Scholarcy	Assist reading	2019	w	NLP	n/a	Freemium	https://www.scholarcy.com/
SciSpace	Assist reading	2015	w	GPT-3.5/4	n/a	Freemium	https://typeset.io
SciSummary	Assist reading	2023	w	GPT/LLM	Semantic Scholar	Free trial, paid subs.	https://scisummary.com/
Undermind	Assist reading	2023	w	LLM	ArXiv	Freemium	https://www.undermind.ai/
Colandr	Analyze data	2017	w	NLP, ML	n/a	Free	https://www.colandrcommunity.com/

Name	Category	Launch year	App type ²	AI method(s)	Data source(s)	Cost	URL
Dextr (beta)	Analyze data	2021	w	ML	Import	Free	https://www.niehs.nih.gov/research/atniehs/labs/iha/dextr
Dimensions	Analyze data	2021	w	ML	Import	Freemium	https://www.dimensions.ai/
Lateral	Analyze data	2022	w	ML	Import	Freemium	https://www.lateral.io/
Research-Screener	Analyze data	2021	w	ML	Import	Freemium	https://researchscreener.com/
RobotAnalyst	Analyze data	2017	w	ML	Import	Free trial, Paid subs.	https://www.nactem.ac.uk/robotanalyst/
AnswerThis	Cite & write	2024	w	LLM	Semantic Scholar, OpenAlex, arXiv, PubMed, Crossref	Freemium	https://answerthis.io/
Jenni AI	Cite & write	2024	w	LLM	n/a	Freemium	https://jenni.ai/literature-review-generator
Logically ⁵	Cite & write	2023	w	LLM	Semantic Scholar	Freemium	https://afforai.com/
Paper Digest	Cite & write	2018	w	NLP, ML, LLM	n/a	Freemium	https://www.paperdigest.org/
ResearchPal	Cite & write	2023	w	LLM	n/a	Freemium	https://researchpal.co/
Samwell.ai	Cite & write	2024	w	ML	n/a	Freemium	https://www.samwell.ai/
scite	Cite & write	2018	w	Deep learning model	Crossref	Free trial, paid subs.	https://scite.ai/
Unriddle	Cite & write	n/a	w	LLM	Import	Freemium	https://www.unriddle.ai/
Write Wise	Cite & write	2020	w + m	NLP, ML, SA	n/a	Free trial, paid subs.	https://web.writewise.io/
Elicit	Full SLR	2023	w	Different LLMs	Semantic Scholar	Freemium	https://elicit.com/
MySLR	Full SLR	2022	w	ML	Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed etc.	Free	https://myslr.unical.it/
Rayyan	Full SLR	2014	w, m	ML	EBSCO, PubMed, import	Freemium	https://www.rayyan.ai/
RSpace (Iris.AI)	Full SLR	2015	w, m	Content-based	Import	Paid subs.	https://iris.ai/

⁵ Renamed from Afforai in March 2025.

Name	Category	Launch year	App type ²	AI method(s)	Data source(s)	Cost	URL
				recommendation engine			
ScholarAI	Full SLR	2024	w	GPT	n/a	Freemium	https://scholarai.io/
SWIFT Active Screener	Full SLR	2016	w	ML	Import	n/a	https://www.sciome.com/swift-activescreener/
sysrev	Full SLR	2017	w	ML	n/a	Freemium	https://sysrev.com/

Table A.2: AI-Based Literature Review Tools for Life Sciences

Name	Category	Launch year	App type	AI method(s)	Data source(s)	Cost	URL
Abstrackr ⁶	Analyze data	2012	w	ML	n/a	Free	https://abstrackr.cebm.brown.edu/
Covidence	Full SLR	2014	w	n/a	n/a	Free trial, paid subs.	https://www.covidence.org/
DistillerSR AI	Full SLR	2016	w	LLM	PubMed	Paid subs.	https://www.distillersr.com/products/distillersrai
ExaCT	Analyze data		w	n/a	n/a	Free	https://nrc.canada.ca/en/research-development/products-services/software-applications/exactdemo-clinical-information-extraction-system
EPPI-Reviewer	Full SLR	2013	w	n/a	n/a	Paid subs-	https://epi.ioe.ac.uk/EPPIReviewer-Web/
EvidenceHunt	AI-Assistants	2023	w	LLM	PubMed	Freemium	https://evidencehunt.com/
Laser AI	Full SLR			ML, KG	n/a	Paid subs.	https://www.laser.ai/product
LitSuggest	Search & discover	2021	w	ML	PubMed	Free	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/research/litsuggest/
Nested Knowledge	Full SLR	2018	w	LLM	PubMed, import	Free trial, paid subs.	https://nested-knowledge.com/
PICOPortal	Full SLR	2020	w	ML, NLP	Import	Free trial, paid subs.	https://picoportal.org/

⁶ As of March 7, 2025, offline for further development.

Name	Category	Launch year	App type	AI method(s)	Data source(s)	Cost	URL
Pitts.ai	Full SLR	n/a	w	GPT	n/a	n/a	https://health.pitts.ai/
RevMan	Analyze data	n/a	w	ML	n/a	Paid subs.	https://subscribe.cochrane.org/info
Robot Reviewer	Analyze data	n/a	w	ML	Import	Free	https://www.robotreviewer.net/
System Pro	Visualize & explore	2022	w	ML, KG	PubMed	Freemium	https://pro.system.com/landing